

Original paper

Vihodtsevski's collection of the flora of Mt. Vitosha Bulgaria in SOM Herbarium at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences

Aneta LAMBEVSKA-HRISTOVA, Svetlana BANCHEVA*

Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Building 3, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 23, 1113-Sofia, Bulgaria

Received: 26 November 2018 / Accepted: 17 June 2019 /

Summary. The Herbarium (SOM) of the Department of the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, is one of the largest Herbaria in the Balkans. Of particular interest are the specialized collections stored in the herbarium; including the thematic collection of researcher Nikolay Vihodtsevski, which represents the plant diversity of Mt. Vitosha, near Sofia, Bulgaria. Even today, this collection is of great importance for the study of plant diversity in Bulgaria.

Keywords: Bulgaria, Herbarium SOM, vascular plants, Vihodtsevski, Mt. Vitosha.

INTRODUCTION

The Herbarium of the Department of Plant and Fungal Diversity and Resources, which is located at the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research in the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, is the largest and most representative source of specimen-based information about Bulgarian flora, as well as one of the most significant information sources concerning Balkan flora. It has been registered as an internationally recognized herbarium under the acronym SOM in the *Index Herbariorum*. At present the herbarium comprises some 177000 specimens from all higher taxonomic groups of embryophytes – bryophytes, lycopodiophytes, equisetophytes, polypodiophytes, gymnosperms and angiosperms.

Of particular interest are the specialized collections stored in the herbarium. One such the-

matic collection was prepared by the researcher Nikolay Vihodtsevski, representing the plant diversity of Mt. Vitosha, near Sofia, Bulgaria.

The purpose of present study is to inform the botanical community of the existence of specialized collections which are stored in the Herbarium SOM, and to make their use more accessible.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The entire available collection has been reviewed, consisting of 22 carton boxes stored in SOM Herbarium. All samples have been digitized and deposited in the SOM database. The names of taxa have been aligned with current taxonomic schemes for respective families, following *Flora Reipublicae Popularis Bulgaricae* (Jordanov 1963, 1964, 1966, 1970, 1973, 1976, 1979; Velchev 1982, 1989), *Flora Reipublicae Bulgaricae* (Kožuharov 1995; Anchev and Kožuharov 2012) and the electronic data base “The Plant

List”, Version 1.1. (2013). Abbreviations of author names follow Brummitt and Powell (1992). Horological elements and abbreviations are as defined by Assyov et al. (2012). Threatened taxa have been identified in accordance with the Bulgarian Biodiversity Law (2002, 2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nikolay Vihodtsevski was born on March 14, 1912 in St. Petersburg, Russia, in the family of a royal officer. After the October Revolution in 1917, his family emigrated from Russia and settled in Sofia, Bulgaria, where Nikolay would spend the rest of his life. He graduated from natural history at Sofia University in 1937 (Tchoumatchenco et al. 2012). Vihodtsevski has had diverse interests in the field of natural sciences - he was an excellent connoisseur of vascular flora and made numerous contributions to the butterfly and fish fauna of Bulgaria. From 1947 to 1952, he was Head of the Department of Natural History at “Uchtehprom” Factory, which produced preparations, models and collections of plants, insects, and skeletons of vertebrates, minerals and rocks. Later, in the period 1952-1966 he was recruited as a technical assistant at the newly established Institute Botany of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (BAS). It was then that Vihodtsevski was engaged in the creation of the Mountain Natural Station of BAS at Mt. Vitosha, where he created a rock garden with many endemic and rare plants from Bulgaria (Stanev 2015). During this period, he focused on the study of the floristic diversity of Mt. Vitosha, and created a rich collection of herbarium specimens. Toward the end of his career (1966-1974), Vihodtsevski began to work at the Herbarium of the Sofia University, where he was appointed Curator.

Vihodtsevski left an impressive collection of herbarium materials from Bulgaria for the preparation and dissemination of Herbarium Centuria by the Institute of Botany. Personally, he entered more than 38000 exsiccates in SOM. Certainly, one of the best of Vihodtsevsky’s collections is devoted to the floristic diversity of the beautiful Mt. Vitosha, which today is kept in SOM.

Vitosha is the fourth highest mountain in Bulgaria. It is located in the immediate proximity of Sofia, between the Rila-Rhodope massif and the Balkan Mountains, surrounded by three large valleys (Sofia, Pernik and Samokov). Vitosha is the only dome-shaped mountain in the country. It has an almost circular shape, with a diameter of 20 to 25 km and an occupancy area of 278 km sq. The highest peak is Cherni Vrah, which rises to 2290 m. More than 50% of the mountain is occupied by forests, 25% are pastures and the rest are rocks. In Vitosha there are over 1500 species of vascular plants that represents nearly 40% of the plant species found in Bulgaria. Today, most of the territory of the mountain is covered by Nature Park Vitosha.

Vihodtsevski’s thematic plant collection, dedicated to the vascular flora of Vitosha Mt., kept in SOM, is stored in 22 boxes and consists of 421 herbarium specimens from 398 taxa, 198 genera and 47 families, including 1 equisetophyte, 12 polypodiophytes, 8 gymnosperms and 377 angiosperms (106 monocotyledons and 271 dicotyledons) (Table 1). The collection includes 33 taxa of conservation significance, which originate from other parts of the country and are grown in the alpine garden created by Vihodtsevski. All specimens are in excellent condition. The richest genera are the following families: Asteraceae (86), Poaceae (73), Scrophulariaceae (34), Boraginaceae (21), Lamiaceae (21), Cyperaceae (20), whereas the richest species are the following genera: *Carex* (13), *Centaurea* (13), *Campanula* (9), *Festuca* (9), *Veronica* (9), *Achillea* (7), *Galium* (7), *Verbascum* (7), etc. In terms of floristic elements, Boreal elements are dominant (48), followed by Eur-As (44), and SubMeds (44), etc. The collection includes some species of importance for conservation efforts: 5 species are Bulgarian endemics, 22 – Balkan endemics and 11 are included in the Bulgarian Biodiversity Low (2002, 2017).

In conclusion, the significance of Vihodtsevski’s collection continues to be of immense importance to this day, as reference exsiccates in studying the taxonomy of the collected plant groups (Asteraceae, Poaceae, Scrophulariaceae, etc.) and the plant diversity of Mt. Vitosha and Bulgaria. We believe that publishing the contents of Vihodtsevski’s collection of Mt. Vitosha will make their use more accessible in studying the floristic diversity of this area.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present study was supported by the National Fund “Scientific Research” of Bulgaria, project ДН-01/7/16.12.2016 ‘Flora of the Republic of Bulgaria, vol. 12: Biological Diversity in Asteraceae subfam. Carduoideae and Cichorioideae’ is gratefully acknowledged. These results were presented at 7 BBC in Novi Sad, Serbia, 10-14. September 2018.

References

- Anchev M, Kožuharov S, editors. 2012. Flora Reipublicae Bulgariae. Vol. 11. Editio Acad. “Prof. Marin Drinov”, Serdicae (in Bulgarian).
- Assyov B, Petrova A, Dimitrov D, Vassilev R, compilers. 2012. Conspectus of the Bulgarian vascular flora. Distribution maps and floristic elements. 4th revised and updated edition. Sofia: Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation.
- Brummitt RK, Powell CE, editors. 1992. Authors of plant names. A list of authors of scientific names of plants, with recommended standard forms of their names, including abbreviations. Kew [UK]: Royal Botanic Gardens.
- Bulgarian Biodiversity Law. 2002. State Gazette no. 77.

- Bulgarian Biodiversity Law, amended and supplemented. 2017. State Gazette no. 76.
- Jordanov D, editor. 1963 – 1979. Flora Reipublicae Popularis Bulgariae. Volumes: 1-7. In Aedibus Academiae Scientiarum Bulgariae, Serdicae (in Bulgarian).
- Kožuharov S, editor. 1995. Flora Reipublicae Bulgariae. Vol. 10. Editio Acad. "Prof. Marin Drinov", Serdicae (in Bulgarian).
- Stanev S. 2015. First builders of Bulgarian botany. Few familiar names from Bulgarian botany. Plovdiv: University Press "Paisiy Hilendarski". p. 601–607.
- Tchoumatchenco P, Petrussenko S, Yanev Y, Dimov G, Lissenko-Chehlarova I. 2012. Bulgarian geologists of Russian origin. Review of the Bulgarian Geological Society. 73(1–3):127–141.
- The Plant List, Version 1.1. 2013. (<http://www.theplantlist.org/>).
- Velchev V, editor. 1982 – 1989. Flora Reipublicae Popularis Bulgariae. Volumes: 8-9. In Aedibus Academiae Scientiarum Bulgariae, Serdicae (in Bulgarian).

Table 1. List of the taxa of Vihodtsevski's collection stored in the Herbarium SOM.

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Adoxaceae	
<i>Adoxa</i>	
<i>Adoxa moschatellina</i> L.	Boreal
Apiaceae	
<i>Angelica</i>	
<i>Angelica pancicii</i> Vandas ex Velen.	*Bal
<i>Heracleum</i>	
<i>Heracleum sibiricum</i> ssp. <i>ternatum</i> (Velen.) Briq.	Eur-As
<i>Opopanax</i>	
¹ <i>Opopanax chironium</i> subsp. <i>bulgaricum</i> (Vel.) N. Andr.	MNS, *Bul
<i>Seseli</i>	
² <i>Seseli tortuosum</i> L.	MNS, subMed
Aristolochiaceae	
<i>Asarum</i>	
<i>Asarum europaeum</i> L.	Eur-Sib
Aspleniaceae	
<i>Asplenium</i>	
<i>Asplenium ruta-muraria</i> L.	Boreal
<i>A. septentrionale</i> (L.) Hoffm.	Boreal
<i>A. trichomanes</i> L.	Kos
Asteraceae	
<i>Achillea</i>	
³ <i>Achillea chrysocoma</i> Friv.	MNS, *Bal
<i>A. crithmifolia</i> Waldst. & Kit.	Pann-Bal
<i>A. grandifolia</i> Friv.	Bal-Anat
<i>A. lingulata</i> Waldst. & Kit.	Carp-Bal
<i>A. millefolium</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>A. multifida</i> (DC.) Boiss.	Carp-Bal
<i>A. nobilis</i> L.	Eur-WAs
<i>Antennaria</i>	
<i>Antennaria dioica</i> var. <i>australis</i> Gris (sub <i>A. dioica</i> f. <i>australis</i>)	Arct-Alp
<i>Anthemis</i>	
⁴ <i>Anthemis carpatica</i> Waldst. & Kit. ex Willd. (sub <i>A. montana</i>)	MNS, Carp-Bal
<i>A. cotula</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>A. ruthenica</i> M. Bieb.	subMed
<i>Arctium</i>	
<i>Arctium lappa</i> L.	Eur-Med
<i>A. minus</i> (Hill) Bernh.	Eur-As

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Artemisia	
⁵ <i>Artemisia pedemontana</i> Balbis (sub <i>A. caucasica</i>)	MNS, Pont-Med,*BDL
<i>A. vulgaris</i> L.	subBoreal
Bidens	
<i>Bidens tripartita</i> Bojer (sub <i>B. tripartita</i> var. <i>orientalis</i> (Velen.) Sherff)	Boreal
Carduus	
<i>Carduus acanthoides</i> L.	Eur
<i>C. kernerii</i> subsp. <i>scardicus</i> (Griseb.) Kazmi (sub <i>C. scardicus</i> (Griseb.) Wettst.)	*Bal; Eur
Carlina	
<i>Carlina vulgaris</i> L.	Eur-Med
Carthamus	
<i>Carthamus lanatus</i> L.	subMed
Centaurea	
⁶ <i>Centaurea adscendens</i> (Bartl.) Prodan (= <i>C. triumfettii</i> subsp. <i>variegata</i> var. <i>adscendens</i>)	MNS, Eur-Med
<i>C. jacea</i> subsp. <i>angustifolia</i> (DC.) Gremler (sub <i>C. jacea</i> ssp. <i>angustifolia</i> var. <i>pannonica</i> Heuff.)	Illyric-Adriatic
<i>C. nervosa</i> Willd.	Alp-Carp-Bal
⁷ <i>C. orientalis</i> L.	MNS, Pont-Med
<i>C. phrygia</i> L.	Eur
<i>C. phrygia</i> subsp. <i>degeniana</i> (J. Wagner) Stoj. & Acht.	*Bal
<i>C. phrygia</i> subsp. <i>moesiaca</i> (Urum. & J. Wagner) Hayek (sub <i>C. phrygia</i> ssp. <i>phrygia</i> var. <i>moesiaca</i> (Urum. & J. Wagner) Hayek)	*Bul
<i>C. phrygia</i> subsp. <i>phrygia</i> var. <i>phrygia</i> L.	Eur
<i>C. scabiosa</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>C. scabiosa</i> subsp. <i>fritschii</i> (Hayek) Hayek	Eur-Sib
<i>C. stenolepis</i> A. Kern. (sub <i>C. phrygia</i> ssp. <i>stenolepis</i> (A. Kern.) Gugler)	subMed
<i>C. stoebe</i> subsp. <i>australis</i> (A. Kern.) Greuter (sub <i>C. micranthos</i> (Griseb.) Hayek)	subMed
⁸ <i>C. stoebe</i> subsp. <i>australis</i> (A. Kern.) Greuter (= <i>C. stoebe</i> subsp. <i>micranthos</i> var. <i>australis</i> f. <i>genuina</i>)	MNS, subMed
Chrysanthemum	
<i>Chrysanthemum corymbosum</i> L.	Eur-Med
<i>Ch. macrophyllum</i> Waldst. & Kit.	Eur
Cicerbita	
<i>Cicerbita alpina</i> (L.) Wallr. (sub <i>Mulgedium alpinum</i> Less.)	Eur-Med
Cichorium	
<i>Cichorium intybus</i> L.	Eur-Sib
Cirsium	
<i>Cirsium appendiculatum</i> Griseb.	*Bal
<i>C. arvense</i> (L.) Scop.	Eur-As
<i>C. candelabrum</i> Griseb.	Carp-Bal
<i>C. canum</i> (L.) All.	Eur-Med
<i>C. heterotrichum</i> Pančić	subBal
<i>C. vulgare</i> (Savi) Ten (sub <i>C. lanceolatum</i> (L.) Hill)	Eur-Med
Cota	
<i>Cota tinctoria</i> subsp. <i>gaudium-solis</i> (Velen.) Oberpr. & Greuter (sub <i>Anthemis tinctoria</i> var. <i>gaudium-solis</i>)	*Bul, BDL
Crepis	
<i>Crepis biennis</i> Lapeyr.	subMed
<i>C. setosa</i> Haller f.	Eur-Med

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Crupina	
<i>Crupina vulgaris</i> Pers. ex Cass.	subMed
Doronicum	
<i>Doronicum austriacum</i> Jacq.	Eur-Med
<i>D. columnae</i> Ten.	Pont-Med
<i>D. orientale</i> Hoffm. (sub <i>D. columnae</i> var. <i>orientale</i>)	Bal-Dac
Erigeron	
<i>Erigeron acer</i> L.	Boreal
<i>E. canadensis</i> L.	N. America (alien species)
Filago	
<i>Filago arvensis</i> L.	Eur-Med
Gnaphalium	
<i>Gnaphalium sylvaticum</i> L.	Eur-Sib
Hieracium	
<i>Hieracium cymosum</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>H. hoppeanum</i> Wallr. ex Nyman	Eur-Med
<i>H. murorum</i> L.	Eur
<i>H. pannosum</i> Boiss.	Bal-Anat
<i>H. pilosella</i> L.	Eur-Med
<i>H. praecurrens</i> Vuk.	Alp-Bal
<i>H. sparsum</i> Friv.	subMed
Hypochaeris	
<i>Hypochaeris maculata</i> L.	Eur-Sib
Inula	
<i>Inula britannica</i> L.	Eur-Med
<i>I. ensifolia</i> L.	Eur-Med
<i>I. hirta</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>I. oculus-christi</i> L.	Eur-Med
Jacobaea	
<i>Jacobaea abrotanifolia</i> subsp. <i>carpathica</i> (Herbich) B.Nord. & Greuter	Carp-Bal
<i>J. pancicii</i> (Degen) Vladimirov & Raab-Straube (sub <i>Senecio pancicii</i> Degen)	*Bal
Lapsana	
<i>Lapsana communis</i> L. (sub <i>L. communis</i> var. <i>glandulosa</i>)	Eur-Sib
Leontodon	
<i>Leontodon asper</i> (Waldst. & Kit.) Poir.	Eur-Med
<i>L. autumnalis</i> L.	Eur-Sib
Leucanthemum	
<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i> (Vaill.) Lam.	Eur-Sib
Matricaria	
<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> L.	Eur-As
<i>M. caucasica</i> (Willd.) Poir.	Bal-Cauc
Mycelis	
<i>Mycelis muralis</i> (L.) Dumort. (sub <i>Lactuca muralis</i> (L.) Fresen.)	Med
Petasites	
<i>Petasites albus</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Eur-Pont
Prenanthes	
<i>Prenanthes purpurea</i> L.	Eur-Med
Senecio	
<i>Senecio vulgaris</i> L.	Eur-As
Serratula	
<i>Serratula tinctoria</i> L.	Eur-Sib

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Solidago	
<i>Solidago virga-aurea</i> L.	Boreal
Tanacetum	
<i>Tanacetum vulgare</i> L.	Eur-Sib
Taraxacum	
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i> (L.) Weber ex F.H.Wigg.	Eur-Med
Tragopogon	
<i>Tragopogon orientalis</i> L. (sub <i>T. pratensis</i> var. <i>orientalis</i> (L.) Čelak.)	Eur-Med
Tripleurospermum	
<i>Tripleurospermum inodorum</i> (L.) Sch.Bip. (sub <i>Matricaria inodora</i> L.)	Eur-As
<i>T. tenuifolium</i> (Kit.) Freyn ex Freyn (sub <i>M. tenuifolia</i> (Kit.) Simonk.)	Eur-As
Tussilago	
<i>Tussilago farfara</i> L.	Eur-As
Boraginaceae	
Buglossoides	
<i>Buglossoides arvensis</i> (L.) I. M. Johnst. (sub <i>Lithospermum arvense</i> L.)	Eur-As
<i>B. purpureocaerulea</i> (L.) I. M. Johnst. (sub <i>L. purpureocaeruleum</i> L.)	Eur-As
Cerithe	
<i>Cerithe minor</i> L.	Pont-Med
Cynoglossum	
<i>Cynoglossum montanum</i> L.	subMed
<i>C. officinale</i> L.	SPont
Echium	
<i>Echium vulgare</i> L.	Eur-As
Heliotropium	
⁹ <i>Heliotropium suaveolens</i> M. Bieb.	MNS, subMed
Lappula	
¹⁰ <i>Lappula barbata</i> M. Bieb. Gürke (sub <i>L. echinata</i> Gilib.)	MNS, Med-CAs
Myosotis	
<i>Myosotis alpestris</i> F.W.Schmidt	Eur-Med
<i>M. caespitosa</i> Schultz.	subBoreal
<i>M. incrassata</i> Guss. (sub <i>M. idaea</i> Boiss. et Heldr.)	subMed
<i>M. ramosissima</i> Rochel (sub <i>M. hispida</i> Schlecht.)	subMed
<i>M. scorpioides</i> L. (sub <i>M. palustris</i> v. <i>scabra</i>)	Eur-NAM
<i>M. sparsiflora</i> Mikan. ex Pohl	Eur-As
<i>M. stricta</i> Linl ex Roem. et Schultes	Eur-As
<i>M. sylvatica</i> Hoffm.	Eur-As
Onosma	
¹¹ <i>Onosma arenaria</i> Waldst. & Kit.	MNS, Eur
Pulmonaria	
<i>Pulmonaria officinalis</i> L.	Eur
<i>P. rubra</i> Schott	Carp-Bal
<i>P. rubra</i> Schott - albino plant (sub <i>Pulmonaria rubra</i> f. <i>alba</i>)	Carp-Bal
Symphytum	
<i>Symphytum tuberosum</i> L.	Eur-Med
Brassicaceae	
Aurinia	
<i>Aurinia saxatilis</i> (L.) Desv. (sub <i>Alyssum saxatile</i> L.)	Eur-Med
Campanulaceae	
Campanula	
<i>Campanula abietina</i> Griseb. (sub <i>C. expansa</i> var. <i>abietina</i> f. <i>stefanofii</i>)	Carp-Bal

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
<i>C. alpina</i> Jacq.	Alp-Carp
<i>C. frivaldskyi</i> Steudel	*Bal
<i>C. glomerata</i> L.	Eur-OT
<i>C. moesiaca</i> Velen.	Bal
<i>C. persicifolia</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>C. rapunculoides</i> L.	Eur
<i>C. sparsa</i> Friv.	Bal-Carp;
<i>C. trachelium</i> L.	Boreal
Jasione	
<i>Jasione bulgarica</i> Stoj. & Stef.	*Bul, BDL
<i>J. heldreichii</i> Boiss. & Orph.	Eur-Med
Legousia	
<i>Legousia speculum-veneris</i> (L.) Durande ex Vill. (sub <i>Specularia speculum</i> A.DC.)	Eur-Med
Caprifoliaceae	
Lonicera	
<i>Lonicera caerulea</i> L.	Alp-Med
<i>L. nigra</i> L.	Alp-Bal
<i>L. xylosteum</i> L.	Eur-Sib
Sambucus	
¹² <i>Sambucus deborensis</i> (Koš.) Koš. (sub <i>S. ebulus</i> var. <i>laciniata</i>)	MNS, *Bal
<i>S. nigra</i> L.	Eur-Med
<i>S. racemosa</i> L.	Boreal
Viburnum	
<i>Viburnum lantana</i> L.	Eur-Med
<i>V. opulus</i> L.	Eur-Sib
Caryophyllaceae	
Saponaria	
¹³ <i>Saponaria stranjensis</i> Jordanov	MNS, *Bal, BDL
Convallariaceae	
Polygonatum	
<i>Polygonatum verticillatum</i> (L.) All.	Eur-As
Convolvulaceae	
Convolvulus	
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L.	Kos
Crassulaceae	
Sedum	
<i>Sedum album</i> L.	subMed
<i>S. cepaea</i> L.	subMed
Sempervivum	
¹⁴ <i>Sempervivum zeleborii</i> Schott (sub <i>S. ruthenicum</i> (Koch) Vel.)	MNS, subMed
Cupressaceae	
Juniperus	
<i>Juniperus communis</i> var. <i>saxatilis</i> Pall. (sub <i>J. nana</i> Willd.)	subBoreal
<i>J. sibirica</i> Burgsd.	Boreal
Cuscutaceae	
Cuscuta	
<i>Cuscuta epithimum</i> (L.) L.	Eur
<i>C. monogyna</i> Vahl.	Eur-As
Cyperaceae	
Carex	
<i>Carex atrata</i> L.	Eur

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
<i>C. bueckii</i> Wimm.	<i>Eur</i>
<i>C. caryophyllea</i> Latourr. (sub <i>C. verna</i> Lam.)	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>C. digitata</i> L.	<i>Eur-Sib</i>
<i>C. halleriana</i> Asso	<i>Eur-As</i>
<i>C. hirta</i> L.	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>C. montana</i> L.	<i>Eur-Sib</i>
<i>C. nigra</i> (L.) Reichard (sub <i>C. goodenowii</i> J.Gay)	<i>Alp-Carp</i>
<i>C. pallescens</i> L.	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>C. pilosa</i> Scop.	<i>Eur-As</i>
<i>C. sylvatica</i> Huds.	<i>subMed</i>
<i>C. tricolor</i> Velen.	<i>Bul</i>
<i>C. umbrosa</i> Host	<i>Eur</i>
Eriophorum	
<i>Eriophorum angustifolium</i> Honck. (sub <i>E. polystachyon</i>)	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>E. latifolium</i> Hoppe	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>E. vaginatum</i> L.	<i>Eur-As</i>
Eleocharis	
<i>Eleocharis palustris</i> (L.) Roem. & Schult.	<i>Kos</i>
Isolepis	
<i>Isolepis setacea</i> (L.) R. Br. (sub <i>Scirpus setaceus</i> L.)	<i>Kos</i>
Scirpus	
<i>Scirpus sylvaticus</i> L.	<i>subBoreal</i>
Trichophorum	
<i>Trichophorum cespitosum</i> (L.) Hartm. (sub <i>Scirpus cespitosus</i> L.)	<i>Boreal</i>
Dipsacaceae	
Cephalaria	
<i>Cephalaria uralensis</i> (Murray) Roem. & Schult.	<i>Pont-Med</i>
Knautia	
<i>Knautia arvensis</i> (L.) Coult.	<i>Eur-Sib</i>
<i>K. drymeia</i> Heuff.	<i>Alp-Capr-Bal</i>
Scabiosa	
¹⁵ <i>Scabiosa argentea</i> L. (sub <i>S. ucrainica</i> v. <i>eburnea</i>)	<i>MNS, Bal-Anat</i>
<i>S. ochroleuca</i> L.	<i>Eur-Sib</i>
<i>S. triniifolia</i> Friv. (sub <i>S. silaifolia</i> Velen.)	<i>*Bal</i>
Succisa	
<i>Succisa pratensis</i> Moench	<i>Eur</i>
Dryopteridaceae	
Dryopteris	
<i>Dryopteris dilatata</i> (Hoffm.) A. Gray (sub <i>Nephrodium spinulosum</i> (Müll.) Strempel)	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>D. filix-mas</i> (L.) Schott.	<i>Boreal</i>
Gymnocarpium	
<i>Gymnocarpium dryopteris</i> (L.) Newman (sub <i>Nephrodium dryopteris</i> (L.) Michx.)	<i>Boreal</i>
Polystichum	
<i>Polystichum aculeatum</i> (L.) Roth. ex Mert.	<i>Boreal</i>
Equisetaceae	
Equisetum	
<i>Equisetum hyemale</i> L.	<i>Boreal</i>
Ericaceae	
Arctostaphylos	
<i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i> (L.) Spreng.	<i>Boreal</i>

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Bruckenthalia	
<i>Bruckenthalia spiculifolia</i> (Salisb.) Reincheb.	<i>subMed</i>
Calluna	
¹⁶ <i>Calluna vulgaris</i> (L.) Hull	<i>MNS, subBoreal, *BDL</i>
Vaccinium	
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L.	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>V. uliginosum</i> L.	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>V. vitis-idaea</i> L.	<i>Boreal</i>
Fabaceae	
Anthyllis	
¹⁷ <i>Anthyllis vulneraria</i> subsp. <i>polyphylla</i> (DC.) Nyman p.p.	<i>MNS, Eur-Med</i>
Genista	
<i>Genista depressa</i> M. Bieb.	<i>subMed</i>
<i>G. ovata</i> Waldst. et Kit.	<i>Eur</i>
<i>G. tinctoria</i> L.	<i>Eur-Sib</i>
Trifolium	
¹⁸ <i>Trifolium rubens</i> L.	<i>MNS, Pont-Med</i>
Vicia	
¹⁹ <i>Vicia narbonensis</i> L.	<i>MNS, Eur-As</i>
Fagaceae	
Fagus	
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> L.	<i>Eur</i>
Quercus	
<i>Quercus cerris</i> L.	<i>Eur-subMed</i>
<i>Q. petraea</i> (Matt.) Liebl. (sub <i>Q. sessiliflora</i> Salisb. and <i>Q. sessilis</i> Ehrh.)	<i>Eur</i>
<i>Q. pubescens</i> Willd.	<i>Eur-subMed</i>
Gentianaceae	
Centaurium	
<i>Centaurium erythraea</i> Raf. (sub <i>Erythraea centaurium</i> (L.) Pers.)	<i>subMed</i>
<i>C. erythraea</i> subsp. <i>rumelicum</i> (Velen.) Melderis (sub <i>Erythraea centaurium</i> ssp. <i>rumelica</i>)	<i>subMed</i>
Gentiana	
<i>Gentiana asclepiadea</i> L.	<i>Eur</i>
<i>G. bulgarica</i> (Velen.) Holub	<i>Pont</i>
<i>G. cruciata</i> L.	<i>Eur-Sib</i>
<i>G. punctata</i> L.	<i>Alp-Carp, *BDL</i>
<i>G. verna</i> L.	<i>Eur-As</i>
Gesneriaceae	
Haberlea	
²⁰ <i>Haberlea rhodopensis</i> Friv.	<i>MNS, *Bal, BDL</i>
Hyacinthaceae	
Muscari	
<i>Muscari botryoides</i> (L.) Mill.	<i>Med</i>
Ornithogalum	
<i>Ornithogalum montanum</i> Ten.	<i>Alp-Bal</i>
<i>O. orthophyllum</i> subsp. <i>orbelicum</i> (Velen.) Zahar. (sub <i>O. tenuifolium</i> ssp. <i>orbelicum</i> Velen.)	<i>*Bul</i>
Scila	
<i>Scilla bifolia</i> L.	<i>Pont-subMed</i>

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Iridaceae	
Crocus	
<i>Crocus veluchensis</i> Herb.	*Bal
Gladiolus	
<i>Gladiolus imbricatus</i> L.	Eur-sMed
Iris	
<i>Iris variegata</i> L.	subMed
Lamiaceae	
Acinos	
<i>Acinos arvensis</i> (Schur) Dandy (<i>Satureja acinos</i> (L.) Scheele)	Eur-Med
Betonica	
²¹ <i>Betonica haussknechtii</i> (Nyman) Hausskn. (sub <i>Stachys balcanica</i> P.W. Ball.)	MNS, Bal*BDL
<i>B. officinalis</i> L.	subMed
Hyssopus	
²² <i>Hyssopus officinalis</i> L.	MNS, Eur-As
Salvia	
²³ <i>Salvia forskahlei</i> L.	MNS, SEux, *BDL
<i>S. glutinosa</i> L.	Eur-As
<i>S. nemorosa</i> L.	Eur-OT
<i>S. verticillata</i> L.	subMed
Satureja	
<i>Satureja montana</i> L. (sub <i>S. montana</i> v. <i>genuina</i>)	Pont-Med
Scutellaria	
<i>Scutellaria altissima</i> L.	Eur
<i>S. columnae</i> All.	subMed
Stachys	
<i>Stachys alpina</i> L.	Alp-Carp
<i>S. germanica</i> L.	Eur-subMed
<i>S. sylvatica</i> L.	Eur-As
Teucrium	
<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i> L.	subMed
<i>T. polium</i> L.	Pont-Med
Thymus	
²⁴ <i>T. comptus</i> Friv. (sub <i>T. glaucus</i> nom. Illegit.)	MNS, *Bal
<i>T. pannonicus</i> All. (sub <i>T. marschallianus</i> Bees.)	Eur
<i>T. pulegioides</i> L.	Eur
<i>T. pulegioides</i> subsp. <i>montanus</i> (Benth.) Ronniger (sub <i>T. pulegioides</i> var. <i>montanus</i>)	Eur
<i>T. vandasii</i> Velen. (sub <i>T. balcanus</i> Borbás.)	Eur-Med
Lentibulariaceae	
Pinguicula	
<i>Pinguicula balcanica</i> Casper (sub <i>P. vulgaris</i> L.)	*Bal
Liliaceae	
Erythronium	
<i>Erythronium dens-canis</i> L.	Med
Gagea	
<i>Gagea pratensis</i> (Pers.) Dumort.	Eur
Paris	
<i>Paris quadrifolia</i> L.	Eur-Sib

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Melanthiaceae	
Veratrum	
<i>Veratrum lobelianum</i> Bernh.	<i>Eur-As</i>
<i>V. nigrum</i> L.	<i>Eur-As</i>
Molluginaceae	
Mollugo	
²⁵ <i>Mollugo cerviana</i> (L.) Ser.	<i>MNS, Pont-Med</i>
Oleaceae	
Fraxinus	
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> L.	<i>Eur-Med</i>
<i>F. ornus</i> L.	<i>subMed</i>
Ligustrum	
<i>Ligustrum vulgare</i> L.	<i>subMed</i>
Ophioglossaceae	
Botrychium	
<i>Botrychium lunaria</i> (L.) Sw	<i>Boreal</i>
Pinaceae	
Abies	
<i>Abies alba</i> Mill.	<i>Boreal</i>
Picea	
<i>Picea abies</i> (L.) H. Karst. (sub <i>P. excelsa</i> Link)	<i>Boreal</i>
Pinus	
<i>Pinus mugo</i> Turra (sub <i>P. montana</i> Mill.)	<i>Alp-Carp-Bal</i>
<i>P. peuce</i> Griseb.	<i>*Bal</i>
<i>P. sylvestris</i> L.	<i>subBoreal</i>
Plantaginaceae	
Kickxia	
²⁶ <i>Kickxia spuria</i> (L.) Dumort. (sub. <i>Elatinoides spuria</i>)	<i>MNS, subMed</i>
Plantago	
<i>Plantago atrata</i> Hoppe (sub <i>P. montana</i> Griseb.)	<i>subMed</i>
²⁷ <i>P. coronopus</i> L.	<i>MNS, Eur-Med</i>
<i>P. lanceolata</i> L.	<i>Kos</i>
<i>P. major</i> L.	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>P. media</i> L.	<i>Boreal</i>
²⁸ <i>P. scabra</i> Moench (sub <i>P. arenaria</i>)	<i>MNS, Eur-Sib</i>
<i>P. subulata</i> L. (sub <i>P. carinata</i> Schrad. ex Mert. & W.D.J. Koch)	<i>Med</i>
Plumbaginaceae	
Armeria	
<i>Armeria rumelica</i> Boiss.	<i>*Bal</i>
Poaceae	
Agrostis	
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i> L.	<i>Boreal</i>
<i>A. rupestris</i> All.	<i>Alp-Carp-Bal</i>
Alopecurus	
<i>Alopecurus gerardii</i> Vill.	<i>Alp-Ap-Bal</i>
<i>A. pratensis</i> L.	<i>Eur-As</i>
<i>A. utriculatus</i> Sol.	<i>SubMed</i>
Anthoxanthum	
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i> L.	<i>Eur-As</i>
Apera	
<i>Apera spica-venti</i> (L.) P. Beauv	<i>subBoreal</i>

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Arrhenatherum	
<i>Arrhenatherum elatius</i> (L.) P. Beauv. ex J. Presl & C. Presl	Eur-As
Avena	
<i>Avena planiculmis</i> (Schrader) W. Sauer & Chmel. (sub <i>A. planiculmis</i> Schrader)	Bal-Anat
<i>A. pubescens</i> Huds.	SSib
Bothriochloa	
<i>Bothriochloa ischaemum</i> (L.) Keng (sub <i>Andropogon ischaemum</i> L.)	subMed-As
Brachypodium	
<i>Brachypodium pinnatum</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	SSib
Briza	
<i>Briza maxima</i> L. f. <i>maxima</i>	Med
<i>B. media</i> L.	Eur
Bromus	
<i>Bromus arvensis</i> L.	Eur-As
<i>B. inermis</i> Leyss. (sub <i>F. poiformis</i> Pers.)	Eur-As
<i>B. mollis</i> L.	Boreal
<i>B. ramosus</i> Huds. (sub <i>B. asper</i> Murray)	subMed-As
<i>B. squarrosus</i> L.	subMed
<i>B. tectorum</i> L.	Boreal
Calamagrostis	
<i>Calamagrostis arundinacea</i> (L.) Roth.	subBoreal
<i>C. epigeios</i> (L.) Roth.	Eur-As
Cynosurus	
<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i> L.	Eur
<i>C. echinatus</i> L.	subMed
Dactylis	
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i> L.	Eur-As
Dasyphyrum	
<i>Dasyphyrum villosum</i> (L.) Borbás (sub <i>Haynaldia villosa</i> (L.) Schur.)	subMed
Deschampsia	
<i>Deschampsia caespitosa</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Boreal
Digitaria	
<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> (L.) Scop. (sub <i>Panicum sanguinale</i> L.)	Cos
Elymus	
<i>Elymus caninus</i> (L.) L. (sub <i>Agropyron caninum</i> (L.) P. Beauv)	Boreal
Eragrostis	
<i>Eragrostis pilosa</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Cos
Festuca	
<i>Festuca airoides</i> Lam. (sub <i>F. ovina</i> var. <i>supina</i> Hack.)	Boreal
<i>F. arundinacea</i> Schreb. (sub <i>F. elatior</i> L.)	Pont-SAs
<i>F. dalmatica</i> (Hack.) K.Richt.	subMed
<i>F. gigantea</i> (L.) Vill.	Boreal
<i>F. heterophylla</i> Lam. (sub <i>F. heterophylla</i> f. <i>leiophylla</i> (Hack) Richt.)	Boreal
<i>F. paniculata</i> (L.) Schinz & Thell. (sub <i>F. spadicea</i> L.)	Alp-Carp-Bal
<i>F. pseudovina</i> Hack. ex Wiesb. var. <i>tenuis</i> (Hack.) Acht.	subMed
<i>F. rubra</i> L. (sub <i>F. fallax</i> Thuill.)	Boreal
<i>F. valida</i> (R.Uechtr.) Péntzes (sub <i>Festuca varia</i> ssp. <i>varia</i> var. <i>valida</i>)	*Bal

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Glyceria	
<i>Glyceria fluitans</i> (L.) R. Br.	Kos
<i>G. plicata</i> Fr. var. <i>plicata</i>	Kos
Holcus	
<i>Holcus lanatus</i> L.	Eur
Hordeum	
<i>Hordeum murinum</i> L.	Boreal
<i>H. secalinum</i> Schreb.	Boreal
Hordelymus	
<i>Hordelymus europaeus</i> (L.) Jess. ex Harz (sub <i>H. silvaticum</i> Huds.)	Eur-sMed
Koeleria	
<i>Koeleria macrantha</i> (Ledeb.) Schult. (sub <i>K. gracilis</i> Pers.)	Eur
Lerchenfeldia	
<i>Lerchenfeldia flexuosa</i> (L.) Schur (sub <i>D. flexuosa</i> (L.) Trin.)	Boreal
Lolium	
<i>Lolium perenne</i> L.	Eur-As
Melica	
<i>Melica uniflora</i> Retz.	Eur
Milium	
<i>Milium effusum</i> L.	subBoreal
Nardus	
<i>Nardus stricta</i> L.	Arct-Alp
Pennisetum	
<i>Pennisetum glaucum</i> (L.) R.Br. (sub <i>Setaria glauca</i> (L.) P. Beauv.)	Adv.
Phalaris	
<i>Phalaris canariensis</i> L.	Med
Phleum	
<i>Phleum alpinum</i> L.	Arct-Alp
<i>P. montanum</i> K. Koch (sub <i>P. serrulatum</i> Boiss)	Med
<i>P. phleoides</i> (L.) H. Karst. (sub <i>P. boehmeri</i> Wibel)	Eur-As
<i>P. pratense</i> L.	Eur-subMed
<i>P. pratense</i> var. <i>nodosum</i> (L.) Schrad.	Eur-subMed
Poa	
<i>Poa alpina</i> L.	Boreal
<i>P. annua</i> L.	Kos
<i>P. bulbosa</i> L.	Eur-As
<i>P. compressa</i> L.	Eur-subMed
<i>P. nemoralis</i> L.	Boreal
<i>P. trivialis</i> L. (sub <i>P. silvicola</i> Guss.)	Boreal
<i>P. ursina</i> Velen.	*Bal
Polypogon	
²⁹ <i>Polypogon monspeliensis</i> (L.) Desf.	MNS, Kos
Sclerochloa	
<i>Sclerochloa dura</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Eur-As
Sesleria	
<i>Sesleria comosa</i> Velen.	*Bal
Setaria	
<i>Setaria viridis</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Boreal
Stipa	
<i>Stipa capillata</i> L.	Pont-Med

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Tragus	
³⁰ <i>Tragus racemosus</i> (L.) All.	MNS, subBoreal
Vulpia	
<i>Vulpia myurus</i> (L.) C.C. Gmel.	subBoreal
<i>V. unilateralis</i> (L.) Stace (<i>V. montana</i> M. Bieb.)	Med-Ch
Polypodiaceae	
Polypodium	
<i>Polypodium vulgare</i> L.	Boreal
Primulaceae	
Anagallis	
<i>Anagallis arvensis</i> ssp. <i>coerulea</i> (L.) Gouan	Kos
Lysimachia	
<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i> L.	Eur
<i>L. punctata</i> L.	Pont-Med
<i>L. vulgaris</i> L.	Eur-As
Primula	
<i>Primula farinosa</i> L.	Eur
<i>P. veris</i> L. (sub <i>P. officinalis</i> (L.) Hill)	Eur-Med
<i>P. veris</i> subsp. <i>suaveolens</i> (Bertol.) Gutermann & Ehrend. (sub <i>P. officinalis</i> var. <i>columnae</i> (Ten.) Maire & Petitm.)	Eur-Med
Soldanella	
<i>Soldanella hungarica</i> Simonk. (sub <i>S. montana</i> Willd.)	Eur
Pteridiaceae	
Pteridium	
<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> (L.) Kuhn	Kos
Ranunculaceae	
Aconitum	
³¹ <i>Aconitum lamarrckii</i> Rchb. (sub <i>A. lycoctonum</i> L.)	MNS, subMed
Clematis	
<i>Clematis viticella</i> L.	Pont-Med
Thalictrum	
³² <i>Thalictrum minus</i> var. <i>olympicum</i> (Boiss. & Heldr.) Strid	MNS, Eur-Sib
Rubiaceae	
Asperula	
<i>Asperula aristata</i> L.f. (sub <i>A. longiflora</i> Waldst. et Kit.)	subMed
<i>A. cynanchica</i> L.	Eur-Med
<i>A. purpurea</i> (L.) Ehrend. (sub <i>G. purpureum</i> L.)	subMed
<i>A. rumelica</i> Boiss. (sub <i>A. cynanchica</i> ssp. <i>montana</i> Waldst. et Kit. ex Willd.)	subMed
Cruciata	
<i>Cruciata laevipes</i> Opiz (sub <i>G. cruciata</i> (L.) Scop.)	subMed-CAs
<i>C. pedemontana</i> (Bellardi) Ehrend. (sub <i>Galium pedemontanum</i> (Bellardi) All.)	Med-CAs
Galium	
<i>Galium aparine</i> L.	Eur-As
<i>G. intermedium</i> Schult. (sub <i>Galium sylvaticum</i> ssp. <i>schultesii</i> Vest.)	subMed
<i>G. odoratum</i> L. Scop. (sub <i>Asperula odorata</i> L.)	Eur-As
<i>G. palustre</i> L.	Boreal
<i>G. rivale</i> (Sibth. & Sm.) Griseb. (sub <i>Asperula rivalis</i> Sibth. et Sm.)	Pont-Sib
<i>G. verum</i> L.	Eur-As
<i>G. verum</i> var. <i>alpinum</i> Krilov ex Serg.	Eur-As
Sherardia	
<i>Sherardia arvensis</i> L.	Med

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Scrophulariaceae	
Digitalis	
<i>Digitalis grandiflora</i> Mill. (sub <i>D. ambigua</i> Murray)	Eur-Sib
<i>D. lanata</i> Enrh.	subMed
³³ <i>D. purpurea</i> L.	MNS, westEur
³⁴ <i>D. viridiflora</i> Lindl.	MNS, *Bal
Euphrasia	
<i>Euphrasia liburnica</i> Wettst.	Carp-Bal
<i>E. pectinata</i> Ten. (sub <i>E. tatarica</i> Fisch. ex Spreng.)	subMed
<i>E. stricta</i> D. Wolff ex. Lehm.	Eur-Med
Linaria	
<i>Linaria dalmatica</i> (L.) Mill.	Med
Melampyrum	
<i>Melampyrum cristatum</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>M. pratense</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>M. sylvaticum</i> L.	Eur
Misopates	
<i>Misopates orontium</i> (L.) Raf. (sub <i>Antirrhinum orontium</i> L.)	Eur-Med
Pedicularis	
<i>Pedicularis occulta</i> Janka	Bul
<i>P. orthantha</i> Griseb.	*Bal
Pseudolysimachion	
³⁵ <i>Pseudolysimachion longifolium</i> (L.) Opiz (sub <i>Veronica spicata</i>)	MNS, Eur-CAs
Rhinanthus	
<i>Rhinanthus minor</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>R. wagneri</i> Degen	subMed
Scrophularia	
<i>Scrophularia scopolii</i> Hoppe ex Pers.	Eur-Med
Verbascum	
<i>Verbascum abietinum</i> Borbás	Bul-Dac
³⁶ <i>V. adrianopolitanum</i> Podp.	MNS, *Bal, BDL
<i>V. formanekii</i> Borbás ex Formanek	Bul
<i>V. longifolium</i> Ten. subsp. <i>pannosum</i> (Vis.) Murb. (sub <i>V. pannosum</i> Vis. & Pančić)	Eur-Med
<i>V. phoeniceum</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>V. phoeniceum</i> subsp. <i>flavidum</i> (Boiss.) Bornm.	Eur-Sib
<i>V. speciosum</i> Schrad.	Eur-Med
Veronica	
<i>Veronica austriaca</i> L. (sub <i>V. jacquinii</i> Baumg.)	Eur-Med
<i>V. beccabunga</i> L.	Eur-As
<i>V. chamaedrys</i> L.	Eur-As
<i>V. hederifolia</i> L. var. <i>hederifolia</i>	Eur-Med
<i>V. officinalis</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>V. scutellata</i> L.	Eur
<i>V. serpyllifolia</i> L.	Boreal
<i>V. teucrium</i> L.	Eur-Sib
<i>V. verna</i> L.	Eur-Sib
Solanaceae	
Atropa	
<i>Atropa bella-donna</i> L.	Eur
Solanum	
<i>Solanum dulcamara</i> L.	Eur-As

Taxon name	Floristic elements and conservation status
Taxaceae	
<i>Taxus</i>	
<i>Taxus baccata</i> L.	<i>Eur-NAm, *BDL</i>
Valerianaceae	
<i>Valeriana</i>	
<i>Valeriana officinalis</i> L.	<i>Eur-Sib</i>
³⁷ <i>V. salina</i> Pleijel	<i>MNS, Scandinavian peninsula</i>
<i>V. tripteris</i> L.	<i>Eur</i>
Woodsiaceae	
<i>Athyrium</i>	
<i>Athyrium filix-femina</i> (L.) Roth	<i>Kos</i>
<i>Cystopteris</i>	
<i>Cystopteris fragilis</i> (L.) Bernh.	<i>Kos</i>

Legend. MNS - Mountain Natural Station of BAS; ¹Originated from an area of Ropotamo river; ²Unknown origin; ³Originated from Slavyanka Mt.; ⁴Originated from Stara planina Mt.; ⁵Originated from cape Kaliacra; ^{6,7}Originated from Golo Bardo Mt.; ⁸Originated from Rhodope Mts.; ⁹Originated from Varna district; ¹⁰Originated from Golo Bardo Mt.; ¹¹Unknown origin; ¹²Originated from Stara planina Mt.; ¹³Originated from Strandzha Mt.; ¹⁴Originated from Varna district; ¹⁵Originated from Zemenska Mt.; ¹⁶Originated from Batashko marsh; ¹⁷Received from Hungary; ¹⁸Alien species, unknown origin; ¹⁹Originated from Balchik area; ²⁰Originated from Rhodope Mts.; ²¹Originated from East Rhodope Mts.; ²²Unknown origin; ²³Originated from Strandzha Mt.; ²⁴Originated from Kyustendil district; ²⁵Originated from Varna district; ²⁶Originated from Varna district; ²⁷Originated from Burgas district; ²⁸Originated from Burgas district; ²⁹Originated from Varna district; ³⁰Originated from Burgas district; ³¹Originated from Strandzha Mt.; ³²Originated from Rhodope Mts.; ³³Alien species; ³⁴Originated from Varna district; ³⁵Originated from Golo Bardo Mt.; ³⁶Originated from Sakar Mt.; ³⁷Originated from Finland; **Bal* - Balcan endemic; **Bul* - Bulgarian endemic; **BDL*-Biodiversity Law.